

Construction of a new Pr³⁺-PVC membrane sensor based on 2,3,4,5-tetra-(4-pyridyl)-thiophene

Somayah Harimi^a, Hassan Ali Zamani^{b*}, Azadeh Tadjarodi^c and Keyvan Bijanzad^c

^aYoung Researchers Club, Quchan Branch, Islamic Azad University, Quchan, Iran

^bDepartment of Applied Chemistry, Mashhad Branch, Islamic Azad University, Mashhad, Iran

E-mail : haszamani@yahoo.com

^cDepartment of Chemistry, Iran University of Science and Technology, Tehran, Iran

Manuscript received online 20 April 2012, accepted 02 May 2012

Abstract : An ion selective electrode Pr³⁺-PVC membrane sensor containing 3% 2,3,4,5-tetra-(4-pyridyl)-thiophene (TPT) as an ionophore, 3% sodium tetraphenyl borate (NaTPB) as an anionic additive, 64% nitrobenzene (NB) as solvent mediator and 30% poly(vinyl chloride) was constructed. This electrode has a wide linear dynamic range from 1.0×10^{-6} to 1.0×10^{-2} M with a Nernstian slope of 20.2 ± 0.5 mV per decade and a low detection limit of 5.3×10^{-7} M in the pH range of 3.0–8.4, while the response time was rapid (~5 s). The developed electrode shows a good selectivity for Pr³⁺ ions respect to a large number of alkali, alkaline earth, transition and heavy metal ions. It was employed as an indicator electrode in the potentiometric titration of Pr³⁺ ions with EDTA. This sensor was also to the determination of fluoride ion in mouth wash preparations and the monitoring of Pr³⁺ in mixtures of three different ions.

Keywords : PVC membrane, sensor, potentiometry, ion-selective electrode.

Introduction

Praseodymium is a soft silvery metallic element, and belongs to the lanthanide group. Praseodymium and praseodymium compounds are used as a core material for carbon arc lights, fiber optic cables as a doping agent and glasses and enamels a yellow color^{1,2}. Many techniques have been developed in order to determine the value of Pr³⁺ in real samples such as : Absorption spectra of the 4f electron transitions, spectrophotometry, inductively couple plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS), inductively couple plasma atomic emission spectrometry (ICP-AES) and some other spectroscopic methods. Almost all of the mentioned methods are expensive and time consuming, as compared to the application of ion selective electrodes (ISEs). ISEs are among the most popular electrochemical devices that usually show fast and selective responses in addition to their low cost and ease of preparation and use. Regarding the fact that there have been some reports on praseodymium electrodes based on different ion carriers³⁻⁵ and also recent experiences on fabrication and development of PVC-membrane ISEs with high selecti-

vity and sensitivity⁶⁻³⁰, we decided to assess the chance of creating a new Pr³⁺ electrode testing 2,3,4,5-tetra-(4-pyridyl)-thiophene (TPT) (Fig. 1) as an excellent ionophore.

Fig. 1. The TPT structure.

Experimental

Reagents and materials :

Reagent grade dibutylphthalate (DBP), nitrobenzene (NB), acetophenon (AP), benzyl acetate (BA), high-molecular weight polyvinylchloride (PVC) and tetrahydrofuran (THF) were purchased from Fluka and Aldrich. The ligand 2,3,4,5-tetra-(4-pyridyl)-thiophene (TPT) was synthesized and purified as described elsewhere³¹. Re-

agent grade of chloride and nitrate salts of used cations were purchased from Merck and Aldrich. All solutions were prepared using doubly distilled deionized water.

EMF measurements :

All EMF measurements were carried out with the following assembly :

Ag-AgCl | 1.0×10^{-3} M PrCl₃ | PVC membrane : test solution | Hg-Hg₂Cl₂, KCl (satd).

A Corning ion analyser 250 pH/mV meter was used for the potential measurements at 25.0 °C. Activities were calculated according to the Debye-Huckel procedure³².

The membrane preparation :

30 mg of the powdered PVC and 64 mg of the NB plasticizer were completely blended in 5 mL of THF. Then, 3 mg of NaTPB and 3 mg of the TPT ionophore were added to this mixture. The solution, after being mixed well, was transferred into a glass dish of 2 cm in diameter. The THF content of the mixture was evaporated slowly, until an oily concentrated mixture was obtained. A Pyrex tube (3–5 mm o.d.) was dipped into the mixture for about 10 s, in order to achieve a transparent membrane formation of about 0.3 mm in thickness^{20–30}. In the end, the tube was removed from the solution, kept at room temperature for 12 h and filled with an internal filling solution (1.0×10^{-3} M PrCl₃). The electrode was conditioned for 24 h by soaking in a 1.0×10^{-3} M PrCl₃ solution. As an internal reference electrode, a silver/silver chloride coated wire was used.

Results and discussion

Sensor potential response :

In preliminary experiments, in order to check selec-

tivity of ionophore toward lanthanide cations, the TPT ligand was tested as an ionophore for the preparation of a variety of ions, mono-, di- and tri-valent metal ion-selective electrodes. Among different cations tested, Pr³⁺ demonstrated the most sensitive response to the PVC membrane based on TPT and seemed to be suitably determined by the PVC membrane, based on the TPT ligand. This is likely due to the high TPT selectivity for Pr³⁺ ions over other metal ions, together with the quick exchange kinetics of the resulting Pr³⁺-TPT complex.

Effect of membrane composition :

The presence of lipophilic anions in cationic-selective membrane electrodes not only diminishes the ohmic resistance, but also in poor extraction capacities, increases the sensitivity of the membrane electrodes^{33–36}. The art sensitivity and selectivity of a given ion carrier significantly depends on the membrane ingredients, the nature of the solvent mediator and the additive^{37–42}. To investigate these effects, the nature and amount of the plasticizer and the additive on the potential response of the constructed Pr³⁺ electrode were performed and the results are summarized in Table 1. Evidently, the increase of the ionophore amount up to a value of 3% provides the optimum sensitivity in the presence of 3% NaTPB along with 54% polar solvent (NB). Among the four different solvent mediators were tested, NB acts superior respect to DBP, AP and BA. This phenomenon can be due to the dielectric constant of the plasticizer on membrane phase as well as the mobility of the ionophore and its complex. All the same, the membranes with a composition of 30% PVC, 3% TPT, 3% NaTPB and 64% NB exhibit a Nernstian potential response.

Table 1. Optimization of the membrane ingredients

No.	Composition (wt %)				Linear range (M)	Slope (mV/decade)
	PVC	Plasticizer	TPT	NaTPB		
1	30	NB, 66	2	2	$1.0 \times 10^{-2} - 1.0 \times 10^{-5}$	19.7 ± 0.3
2	30	BA, 66	2	2	$1.0 \times 10^{-2} - 1.0 \times 10^{-5}$	16.2 ± 0.5
3	30	AP, 66	2	2	$1.0 \times 10^{-2} - 1.0 \times 10^{-5}$	17.5 ± 0.4
4	30	DBP, 66	2	2	$1.0 \times 10^{-2} - 1.0 \times 10^{-5}$	14.4 ± 0.5
5	30	NB, 68	2	0	$1.0 \times 10^{-2} - 1.0 \times 10^{-4}$	15.2 ± 0.2
6	30	NB, 67	2	1	$1.0 \times 10^{-2} - 1.0 \times 10^{-5}$	15.5 ± 0.4
7	30	NB, 65	2	3	$1.0 \times 10^{-2} - 1.0 \times 10^{-6}$	17.7 ± 0.6
8	30	NB, 66	1	3	$1.0 \times 10^{-2} - 1.0 \times 10^{-5}$	16.5 ± 0.3
9	30	NB, 64	3	3	$1.0 \times 10^{-2} - 1.0 \times 10^{-6}$	20.2 ± 0.5

Calibration curve and lifetime :

The potential response of the Pr^{3+} PVC-based membrane sensor at varying concentrations of praseodymium solution (Fig. 2) indicates a linear working concentration range from 1.0×10^{-6} to 1×10^{-2} M. The slope of the calibration graph was 20.2 ± 0.5 mV per decade of praseodymium ions concentration. The detection limit, defined as the praseodymium concentration obtained when extrapolating the linear region of the calibration graph to the base line potential, was 5.3×10^{-7} M. Daily, the sensor was used for one hour, washed and dried. Its usage was found to last for at least 8 weeks. In the end of this time period, the electrode slope reduced (from 20.2 to 17.8 mV per decade).

Fig. 2. Calibration curves of the TPT-based Pr^{3+} electrode with the membrane composition of no. 9.

pH effect :

In an approach to understanding the impact of pH on the electrode response, the potential was measured at one particular concentrations of the Pr^{3+} solution (1.0×10^{-3} M), from the pH value of 1.5 up to 11.0 (Fig. 3) (concentrated NaOH or HCl solutions were employed for the pH adjustment). This figure shows that the potential response of the sensor is independent of pH, in the pH range of 2.9–9.0. The observed drift at higher pH values could be due to the formation of some hydroxyl complexes of Pr^{3+} ions in solution.

Fig. 3. pH effect of the test solution (1.0×10^{-3} M of Pr^{3+}) on the potential response of the praseodymium ion-selective electrode with the membrane composition of no. 9.

Response time :

Dynamic response time is an important factor, for the evaluation any sensor. The dynamic response time of the membrane was measured at various concentrations (1.0×10^{-6} to 1.0×10^{-2} M) of the test solutions. The reported results in Fig. 4 illustrate that in the whole concentration range the electrode reaches its equilibrium response very fast (~ 5 s).

Fig. 4. Dynamic response time of the praseodymium electrode with the membrane composition of no. 9 for step changes in the Pr^{3+} concentration : (A) 1.0×10^{-6} M, (B) 1.0×10^{-5} M, (C) 1.0×10^{-4} M, (D) 1.0×10^{-3} M, (E) 1.0×10^{-2} M.

Selectivity of the Pr^{3+} sensor :

The selectivity behavior is obviously one of the most important characteristics of an ion-selective electrode, determining the possibility of a reliable measurement in the target sample. In this research, the potential responses

of the recommended Pr³⁺ membrane sensor to a wide variety of cations were investigated through the matched potential method (MPM)⁴³⁻⁴⁵. The matched potential method selectivity coefficient, K^{MPM} , is then given by the resulting primary ion to the interfering ion activity (concentration) ratio, $K^{MPM} = \Delta a_A/a_B$. The resulting selectivity coefficient values are summarized in Table 2. The selectivity coefficients for the all mono and divalent and trivalent ions are smaller than 5.2×10^{-3} and they can not disturb the functioning of the Pr³⁺ membrane electrode.

Table 2. Selectivity coefficients of Pr³⁺ electrodes

Interfering ions	$K_{Pr,B}^{MPM}$	Interfering ions	$K_{Pr,B}^{MPM}$
Tb ³⁺	5.2×10^{-3}	Na ⁺	1.0×10^{-4}
Dy ³⁺	1.0×10^{-3}	K ⁺	2.3×10^{-4}
Ho ³⁺	8.7×10^{-4}	Ca ²⁺	4.4×10^{-4}
Eu ³⁺	3.2×10^{-3}	Cu ²⁺	3.0×10^{-3}
Nd ³⁺	2.8×10^{-3}	Co ²⁺	6.3×10^{-4}
Sm ³⁺	7.2×10^{-4}	Cd ²⁺	7.2×10^{-4}
Cr ³⁺	7.6×10^{-4}	Ni ²⁺	8.5×10^{-4}
Fe ³⁺	1.0×10^{-3}	Pb ²⁺	6.8×10^{-4}
Al ³⁺	4.7×10^{-3}	-	-

Table 3 lists and compares the selectivity coefficients, slope, response time, pH range, detection limit, Pr³⁺ sensor concentration range with those of the best formerly reported Pr³⁺ electrodes^{4,5}. As it is obvious, the selectivity coefficients for the majority of the cations, concern-

Table 3. Comparison of previous reported Pr³⁺ ion selective electrode with proposed sensor

Sensor	Ref. 4	Ref. 5	This work
Slope (mV per decade)	21.1	19.6 ± 0.4	20.2 ± 0.5
LR (mol L ⁻¹)	1.0×10^{-6} to 1.0×10^{-2}	1.0×10^{-6} to 1.0×10^{-2}	1.0×10^{-6} to 1.0×10^{-2}
DL (mol L ⁻¹)	8.0×10^{-7}	4.3×10^{-7}	5.3×10^{-7}
pH	3.5 to 8	2.8 to 8.7	2.9 to 9.0
Response time (s)	~20	~10	~5
$\log K_{sel} > -2.3$	Er ³⁺ , Sm ³⁺ , Lu ³⁺ , Eu ³⁺ , Ce ³⁺ , Gd ³⁺ , La ³⁺ , Nd ³⁺	Gd ³⁺ , La ³⁺ , Eu ³⁺ , Cr ³⁺ , Ca ²⁺	-

ing the parameters of response time, detection limit, pH and tested electrode concentration range, are better in comparison with the previous reported Pr³⁺ sensors.

Analytical application :

The electrode was found to work well under the laboratory conditions and sensor was used as an indicator electrode in the titration of a $1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ Pr³⁺ ion solution with a standard $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ EDTA. The resulting titration curve is shown in Fig. 5 and shows that, the sensor is capable of monitoring the amounts of Pr³⁺ ions in such measurements. The proposed Pr³⁺ sensor was also applied for the determination of Pr³⁺ ions concentration in mixtures of three different ions. The corresponding results in Table 4 reveal that the recovery of Pr³⁺ ions in all mixtures is acceptable.

Fig. 5. Potential titration curves of 20.0 mL $1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ Pr³⁺ solution with $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ of EDTA.

Conclusion :

In this work, a potentiometric Pr³⁺-selective membrane sensor based on 2,3,4,5-tetra-(4-pyridyl)-thiophene (TPT) as an excellent ion carrier can estimate Pr³⁺ ions in the concentration range from 1.0×10^{-6} to $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ with the slope of 20.2 ± 0.5 mV per decade of activity. Its selectivity towards the Pr³⁺ ions was not influenced by the presence of the common alkali, alkaline earth, or transition and heavy metal ions. The membrane sensor was applied to the determination of Pr³⁺ ions concentration in mixtures of different ions.

Table 4. Determination of Pr³⁺ ions in mixtures of different ions

Sr. no.	Composition	Observed content (<i>M</i>)
1.	0.00010 mol L ⁻¹ Pr(NO ₃) ₃ + 0.001 mol L ⁻¹ Eu(NO ₃) ₃ + 0.001 mol L ⁻¹ Dy(NO ₃) ₃	0.000098
2.	0.00010 mol L ⁻¹ Pr(NO ₃) ₃ + 0.001 mol L ⁻¹ Tb(NO ₃) ₃ + 0.001 mol L ⁻¹ Nd(NO ₃) ₃	0.000096
3.	0.00010 mol L ⁻¹ Pr(NO ₃) ₃ + 0.001 mol L ⁻¹ Ho(NO ₃) ₃ + 0.001 mol L ⁻¹ Nd(NO ₃) ₃	0.000101
4.	0.00010 mol L ⁻¹ Pr(NO ₃) ₃ + 0.001 mol L ⁻¹ Sm(NO ₃) ₃ + 0.001 mol L ⁻¹ Er(NO ₃) ₃	0.000103
5.	0.00010 mol L ⁻¹ Pr(NO ₃) ₃ + 0.001 mol L ⁻¹ Fe(NO ₃) ₃ + 0.001 mol L ⁻¹ Cr(NO ₃) ₃	0.000107
6.	0.00010 mol L ⁻¹ Pr(NO ₃) ₃ + 0.001 mol L ⁻¹ KNO ₃ + 0.001 mol L ⁻¹ Mg(NO ₃) ₂	0.000097
7.	0.00010 mol L ⁻¹ Pr(NO ₃) ₃ + 0.001 mol L ⁻¹ Ca(NO ₃) ₂ + 0.001 mol L ⁻¹ NaNO ₃	0.000102
8.	0.00010 mol L ⁻¹ Pr(NO ₃) ₃ + 0.001 mol L ⁻¹ Cd(NO ₃) ₂ + 0.001 mol L ⁻¹ Pb(NO ₃) ₂	0.000105
9.	0.00010 mol L ⁻¹ Pr(NO ₃) ₃ + 0.001 mol L ⁻¹ Ni(NO ₃) ₂ + 0.001 mol L ⁻¹ Co(NO ₃) ₂	0.000097

Acknowledgement

The authors acknowledge the kind financial support provided by the Research Council of Mashhad Branch, Islamic Azad University and Young Researchers Club, Quchan Branch, Islamic Azad University for the preparation of this research.

References

1. <http://www.lenntech.com>
2. <http://www.webelements.com>
3. H. A. Zamani, M. R. Ganjali, P. Norouzi and S. Meghdadi, *Anal. Lett.*, 2008, **41**, 902.
4. M. R. Ganjali, F. S. Mirnaghi, P. Norouzi and M. Adib, *Sens. Actuators (B)*, 2006, **115**, 374.
5. H. A. Zamani, M. Masrournia, S. Sahebnaasagh and M. R. Ganjali, *Anal. Lett.*, 2009, **42**, 555.
6. H. A. Zamani, M. T. Hamed-Mosavian, E. Aminzadeh, M. R. Ganjali, M. Ghaemy, H. Behmadi and F. Faridbod, *Desalination*, 2010, **250**, 56.
7. H. A. Zamani, M. Mohammadhossieni, S. Haji-Mohammadrezazadeh, F. Faridbod, M. R. Ganjali, S. Meghdadi and A. Davoodnia, *Mater. Sci. Eng. (C)*, 2012, **32**, 712.
8. H. A. Zamani, M. Masrournia, M. Rostame-Faroge, M. R. Ganjali and H. Behmadi, *Sensor Lett.*, 2008, **6**, 759.
9. H. A. Zamani, G. Rajabzadeh and M. R. Ganjali, *Sensor Lett.*, 2009, **7**, 114.
10. M. R. Abedi and H. A. Zamani, *E-J. Chem.*, 2011, **8**, S467.
11. H. A. Zamani and H. Behmadi, *E-J. Chem.*, 2012, **9**, 308.
12. H. A. Zamani, *Anal. Lett.*, 2009, **42**, 615.
13. M. R. Abedi and H. A. Zamani, *Anal. Lett.*, 2008, **41**, 2251.
14. H. A. Zamani, *E-J. Chem.*, 2012, **9**, 83.
15. H. A. Zamani, Fatemeh Naghavi-Reyabbi, M. Mohammadhossieni, B. Feizyadeh, M. R. Abedi, F. Faridbod and M. R. Ganjali, *Sensor Lett.*, 2011, **10**, 112.
16. H. A. Zamani, B. Feizyadeh, F. Faridbod and M. R. Ganjali, *Sensor Lett.*, 2011, **9**, 1767.
17. H. A. Zamani, M. Masrournia, S. Sahebnaasagh and M. R. Ganjali, *Anal. Lett.*, 2009, **42**, 555.
18. E. Naddaf and H. A. Zamani, *Anal. Lett.*, 2009, **42**, 2838.
19. M. Nekoei, H. A. Zamani and M. Mohammadhossieni, *Anal. Lett.*, 2009, **42**, 284.
20. M. Mohammadhossieni, H. A. Zamani and M. Nekoei, *Anal. Lett.*, 2009, **42**, 298.
21. H. A. Zamani, M. Rohani, M. Mohammadhosseini, M. R. Ganjali, F. Faridbod and S. Meghdadi, *Sensor Lett.*, 2011, **9**, 1745.
22. H. A. Zamani, M. S. Zabihi, M. Rohani, A. Zangeneh-Asadabadi, M. A. Ganjali, F. Faridbod and S. Meghdadi, *Mater. Sci. Eng. (C)*, 2011, **31**, 409.
23. H. A. Zamani, G. Rajabzadeh, A. Firouz and M. R. Ganjali, *J. Anal. Chem.*, 2007, **62**, 1080.
24. H. A. Zamani, *Anal. Lett.*, 2008, **41**, 1850.
25. V. K. Gupta, R. N. Goyal and R. A. Sharma, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 2009, **647**, 66.
26. H. A. Zamani, R. Kamjoo, M. Mohammadhossieni, M. Zaferoni, Z. Rafati, M. R. Ganjali, F. Faridbod and S. Meghdadi, *Mater. Sci. Eng. (C)*, 2012, **32**, 447.
27. H. A. Zamani, F. Faridbod and M. R. Ganjali, *Mater. Sci. Eng. (C)*, 2013, **33**, 608.
28. H. A. Zamani, A. Zangeneh-Asadabadi, M. Rohani, M. S. Zabihi, J. Fadaee, M. R. Ganjali, F. Faridbod and S. Meghdadi, *Mater. Sci. Eng. (C)*, 2013, **33**, 984.
29. H. A. Zamani, M. R. Ganjali and M. Salavati-Niasari, *Transition. Met. Chem.*, 2008, **33**, 995.
30. S. Chandra and D. R. Singh, *Mater. Sci. Eng. (A)*, 2009, **502**, 107.

31. H. I. Thayer and B. B. Corson, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 2330.
32. S. Kamata, A. Bhale, Y. Fukunaga and A. Murata, *Anal. Chem.*, 1998, **60**, 2464.
33. T. Rosatzin, E. Bakker, Y. Suzuki and W. Simon, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1993, **280**, 197.
34. E. Ammann, E. Pretsch, W. Simon, E. Lindner, A. Bezegh and E. Pungor, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1985, **171**, 119.
35. H. A. Zamani, A. Nezhadali and M. Saghravani, *Anal. Lett.*, 2008, **41**, 2727.
36. H. A. Zamani, F. Naghavi-Reyabbi, F. Faridbod, M. Mohammadhossieni, M. R. Ganjali, A. Tadjarodi and M. Rad, *Mater. Sci. Eng. (C)*, 2013, **33**, 870.
37. E. Bakker, P. Buhlmann and E. Pretsch, *Electroanalysis*, 1999, **11**, 915.
38. H. A. Zamani, M. R. Ganjali, P. Norouzi, A. Tajarodi and Y. Hanifehpour, *J. Chil. Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **52**, 1332.
39. E. Bakker, P. Bühlmann and E. Pretsch, *Chem. Rev.*, 1997, **97**, 3083.
40. H. A. Zamani, M. R. Ganjali, F. Faridbod and M. Salavati-Niasari, *Mater. Sci. Eng. (C)*, 2012, **32**, 564.
41. H. A. Zamani, A. Imani, A. Arvinfar, F. Rahimi, M. R. Ganjali, F. Faridbod and S. Meghdadi, *Mater. Sci. Eng. (C)*, 2011, **31**, 588.
42. H. A. Zamani, M. T. Hamed-Mosavian, E. Hamidfar, M. R. Ganjali and P. Norouzi, *Mater. Sci. Eng. (C)*, 2008, **28**, 1551.
43. S. Matysik, F. M. Matysik, J. Mattusch and W. D. Einicke, *Electroanalysis*, 1998, **10**, 57.
44. H. A. Zamani, G. Rajabzadeh, M. Masrornia, A. Dejbord, M. R. Ganjali and N. Seifi, *Desalination*, 2009, **249**, 560.
45. Y. Umezawa, K. Umezawa and H. Sato, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1995, **67**, 507.